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Review Article

**ADIPOSIS DOLOROSA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF
CLINICAL PRESENTATION AND MANAGEMENT****Daphne Sherine.S¹, Hemapriya.M², Mohan Kumar.J², Manisha.M², Kavya.K².**¹ Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, PSV College of Pharmaceutical Science & Research, Krishnagiri² Undergraduates, PSV College of Pharmaceutical Science & Research, Krishnagiri**1. Abstract:**

Dercum's disease, commonly known as adiposis dolorosa, is an uncommon condition marked by the growth of many, excruciating lipomas in the adipose tissue. Middle-aged women are the main population affected by this ailment, which causes chronic pain that drastically lowers quality of life. Although the exact cause of adiposis dolorosa is unknown, it is thought to be related to immunological, hormonal, and metabolic processes. Clinically, patients present with palpably sore subcutaneous nodules and plaques, frequently accompanied by systemic symptoms such as weakness, weariness, and cognitive impairments. The existence of distinctively painful lipomas is the primary basis for the diagnosis, which frequently necessitates ruling out other disorders that may be comparable. While imaging tests like MRIs and ultrasounds can help assess lipomas, they cannot provide a conclusive diagnosis. The few available treatments are primarily symptomatic and concentrate on managing pain with pharmaceuticals like analgesics and anti-inflammatory medicines as well as physical therapy. Although surgical removal of lipomas is linked to risks and recurrence, it can offer comfort. Novel pharmaceutical methods, liposuction, and injections of local anesthetic are among the emerging remedies being studied. The recurrent and chronic nature of adiposis dolorosa places a significant burden on patients, requiring ongoing study to better understand the underlying causes and find appropriate treatments, as well as interdisciplinary methods to therapy. To understand the pathogenesis and find viable treatment options for this crippling ailment, more research is necessary.

Keywords: Rare disorder, Painful lipomas, Subcutaneous nodules, Middle-aged women, Fatigue.

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2. INTRODUCTION:

Francis Xavier Dercum, a neurologist, originally described Dercum's disease in 1892. This unusual condition, sometimes called Ander's syndrome, Dercum-Vitaut syndrome, Lipomatosis dolorosa (or) Adiposis dolorosa is characterized by many painful subcutaneous lipomas on the trunk and extremities. Obese postmenopausal women are mostly affected with Dercum's illness (female to male ratio about 30:1)¹.

Multiple painful growths of loose connective tissue (fat tissue, or lipomas) under the skin's surface, either superficially or deeply, are the hallmark of Dercum's disease, an uncommon illness. Typically, the lipomata development avoids the dorsal hands, feet, head, and neck. The lipomas range in size from the size of a grape to that of a fist. The majority of people with Dercum's disease have pain, which can vary from a slight discomfort to unbearable anguish when touched².

Dercum's syndrome is characterized by the following:

- Painful fatty masses
- Generalized obesity, typically in menopausal females
- Asthenia, weakness, fatigability
- Mental abnormalities, such as sadness, anxiety, epilepsy, mental disorientation and real dementia³.

2.1 NORMAL FAT:

- ✓ **Distribution:** Due to a combination of lifestyle, hormonal, and hereditary variables, evenly dispersed throughout the body.
- ✓ **Consistency:** Usually malleable and flexible.
- ✓ **Response to diet and exercise:** Can be successfully decreased with restriction, and lifestyle modifications.
- ✓ **Pain:** Not often painful; neither sore nor uncomfortable.
- ✓ **Edema:** does not result in appreciable edema.

Fig

no:2.1 Normal fat vs. Lipedema fat

2.2 LIPEDEMA FAT:

- ✓ **Distribution:** The upper body may stay reasonably slender, while the lower body (legs, thighs, and occasionally arms) is disproportionately affected.
- ✓ **Consistency:** Firm and nodular in consistency, it is frequently compared to little peas or grains under the skin.
- ✓ **Response to diet and exercise:** Affected areas do not shrink proportionately; resistant to conventional weight loss techniques.
- ✓ **Pain:** Frequently uncomfortable, sensitive to touch, and prone to bruise easily
- ✓ **Edema:** Usually results from fluid retention that produces swelling. It can develop secondary lymphedema and tends to get worse throughout the day^{4,5}.

2.1 DEFINITION

Adiposis dolorosa, another name for Dercum's disease, is a uncommon disease identified by numerous painful lipomas, or benign fatty growths, trunk, and upper arms. Dercum's disease is unknown, a mix of genetic, hormonal, and metabolic parameters may at play⁶.

A disease accompanied by various nerve lesions and painful localized fatty swellings. It typically affects women and can result in fatal lung problems. Dercum's disease is an uncommon condition where fatty deposits press against the nerves, causing pain and weakness.

The body may swell in a number of places for no obvious reason. Without medical intervention, the swelling may go down, leaving behind pendulous skin folds or stiffened tissue.

Dercum's disease is described by following criteria:

- ✚ Generalized overweight or obesity
- ✚ Chronic pain (longer than 3 months) in adipose tissue.

Dercum's illness is characterized by painful adipose tissue and fatty deposits, sleep disturbances, rapid heartbeat, shortness of breath, fatigue, joint aches, anxiety, depression, constipation, etc⁷.

2.2 CLASSIFICATION

Adiposis dolorosa is classified into 4 types:

- A. Type 1 (Generalized diffuse form)
- B. Type 2 (Generalized nodular form)
- C. Type 3 (Localized nodular form)
- D. TYPE 4 (Juxta-articular form)

The following parameters are used to classify the disease:

The size of the lumps (larger in all forms of the disease, whereas small in generalized diffuse form).

The distribution of fatty deposits (widespread versus localized near or within the joints)⁸.

TYPES	DESCRIPTION
TYPE I (Generalized diffuse form)	Pain from small adipose deposits and fatty tissue can be felt widely throughout the body, even in places where there are no visible lumps.
TYPE II (Generalized nodular form)	Pain concentrated in different body areas surrounding and within lipomas.
TYPE III (Localized nodular form)	Painful lipomas in few spots.
TYPE IV (Juxta-articular form)	Discouraging fat folds inside or close to large joints, such as the elbow, hip, or knee.

Table no:2.1 Types of Dercum's disease

2.3 STAGES OF DERCUM'S DISEASE

The three phase of lipedema-affecting the lower legs, the thighs, and the entire leg-can be distinguished from one another. It affects the limbs as well in about 30% of cases.

Stage 1:

Smooth skin and tiny nodules appear as the subcutaneous layer thickens and softens.

Stage 2:

Consists of bigger nodules, subcutis thickening and softening, and uneven skin texture.

Stage 3:

Giant nodules cause the subcutaneous layer to thicken and harden, and disfiguring fat lobules form on the inner thighs and knees⁹.

2.4 PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

This is a condensed flow diagram representing Adiposis Dolorosa pathophysiology:

1. Hereditary susceptibility:

Abnormal fat cell growth- Uncontrolled fat cell proliferation is caused by a mutated fat gene.

2. Hormonal imbalance:

Fat cell hyperplasia - Variations in progesterone and estrogen lead to the formation of fat cells.

3. Disorders of the nervous system:

Discomfort signaling- Inflammation of adipose tissue nerve terminals results in persistent discomfort

4. Swelling and pain:

Inflammation - Inflammation brought on by the immune response exacerbates pain and swelling

5. A build-up of fat tissue:

Lipoma formation Superfluous fat cells combine to create excruciating lipomas.

6. Persistent discomfort:

Sensitization to neurons - Extended pain increases sensitivity and perception of pain¹⁰.

2.5 ETIOLOGY

The exact cause of Dercum's disease is unknown, a number of theories have been put forth:

- I. **Genetic factors:** Given that certain cases have been documented to run in families, there may be a hereditary component.
- II. **Endocrine and metabolic abnormalities:** Patients with Dercum's disease often have metabolic abnormalities, such as obesity, and hormonal imbalances, particularly involving estrogen.
- III. **Inflammatory and Autoimmune mechanisms:** It is believed that autoimmune reactions and long-term inflammation play a role in the formation of uncomfortable fat deposits.
- IV. **Nerve system Dysfunction:** The pain other symptoms linked to the illness may be caused by abnormalities in the autonomic nerve system^{11,12,13}.

2.6 EPIDEMIOLOGY

Dercum's disease is 5 to 30 times more common in women than in men, and it typically manifests itself between the ages of 35 and 50.

The precise prevalence of Dercum's disease is yet unknown⁶.

2.7 CHARACTERISTICS

The following are some essential traits:

- I. **Painful Lipomas:** These benign fatty tumors, which are usually located in the trunk, upper arms, and upper legs, are the main symptoms.
- II. **Obesity:** Dercum's disease can affect people of average weight, but it more frequently affects obese people.
- III. **Chronic Pain:** Individuals frequently deal with severe incapacitating chronic pain that lowers their quality of life.

- IV. **Fatigue:** A lot of patients complain of severe weakness and exhaustion, which can make daily tasks difficult.
- V. **Cognitive Dysfunction:** A few patients struggle with cognitive disorders such as mental exhaustion, memory loss, and concentration difficulties.
- VI. **Additional symptoms:** Headache, irritability, sadness, and joint discomfort are a few more symptoms that may exist.
- VII. **Comorbidity:** The illness frequently coexists with other ailments as diabetes, hypertension, and sleep apnea^{6,14,15,16}.

2.8 SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS

- I. **Painful lipomas:** Although the lipomas can occur anywhere on the body, but they are most frequently observed on the upper limbs, trunk and upper legs. The degree of the pain fluctuates and might be either continuous or sporadic.
- II. **Fatigue:** A considerable proportion of patients complain of ongoing exhaustion and a persistent sense of fatigue that does not go away with rest.
- III. **Cognitive dysfunction:** Also known as "brain fog", this condition encompasses issues with mental clarity, memory and focus.
- IV. **Weakness:** It is possible to develop generalized muscle weakness, which can make daily tasks difficult.
- V. **Sleep disturbances:** Insomnia or poor sleep quality can result from pain and other symptoms interfering with sleep.
- VI. **Swelling and fluid retention:** Swelling in the afflicted areas can be uncomfortable for some patients and to their sensation of being heavy.
- VII. **Numbness and tingling:** Some patients report feeling numb or tingly as a result of the pressure lipomas place on their nerves.
- VIII. **Joint discomfort:** While less frequent, some patients experience joint discomfort, which the fatty deposits may make worse.
- IX. **Obesity:** Although Dercum's disease can affect persons of normal, many of its patients are obese^{17,18,19,20,21,22}.

2.9 HISTORY

Discovery and Early Description (1888):

Fig no:2.9 Dr. Francis Xavier Dercum

- American neurologist Dr. Francis Xavier Dercum provided the first description of Dercum's disease in 1888.
- He recognized and reported the disease's symptoms, which include sore, fatty growths in the subcutaneous tissues.
- A rare disease called Dercum's disease, also known as Adiposis dolorosa, is characterized by numerous painful lipomas, or fatty tumors, mainly affecting the upper arms, upper legs, and torso.

Guidiceandrea created the initial clinical classification scheme for AD (also known as Dercum's disease, DD) in **1900**.

- It was as follows:
 - I. Nodular type- A type when there are painful lipomas, usually on the back, thorax, arms, or legs. Occasionally, the lipomas form a confluent mass, while other times they exist in multiple sites. The nodules are palpably painful and range in size.
 - II. Diffuse type- A type having adipose tissue that is diffusely uncomfortable.
 - III. Mixed type- A type with painful nodular masses and diffusely uncomfortable adipose tissue.

Roux and **Vitaut** then refined this categorization in **1901** and presented four cardinal symptoms of DD, which were utilized as diagnostic criteria for a number of years

- I. **Early 20th Century:** As a result of Dercum's pioneering research, more instances were documented, and doctors started to identify the disease's unique clinical manifestation. Severe pain, obesity, chronic exhaustion were frequently mentioned as standout characteristics in these early accounts.
- II. **Mid- 20th Century:** More research was then in an effort to comprehend the pathophysiology and etiology of the illness.

During this time, studies revealed possible connection to defects in the neurological system, endocrine system, and metabolism.

- III. **Late 20th century:** Improvements in pathology and medical imaging allowed for a more accurate diagnosis and identification of the illness. Research focused on the chronic pain that accompanied the painful lipomas and showed how they differed from other lipomas.
- IV. **21st Century developments:** Research in the last few years has concentrated on autoimmune components, genetic variables and possible treatments. The accuracy of diagnosis has increased with the use of contemporary imaging methods like MRI. The function of cytokines and other inflammatory markers in the illness process is being studied in current study.
- V. **Recent advances:** Research into better treatments, such as pain management techniques, surgical alternatives, and drugs that target the underlying inflammatory process, is still ongoing.
- VI. **Initial descriptions:** The manifestation of excruciating subcutaneous fatty deposits was the main emphasis of the disease's early reports. Dercum determined the obesity, and chronic discomfort were the main characteristics of the illness.
- VII. **Recognition and classification:** As time went on, the illness came to be understood as a separate medical disease. It was categorized as one of the uncommon adipose tissue abnormalities. The predominant basis for the diagnostic criteria was clinical symptoms, specifically the well-known painful lipomas.
- VIII. **Research and genetic insights:** The field of study surrounding Dercum's disease grew during the 20th century although no particular gene has been definitively connected to the illness, studies have looked into possible genetics components. A hereditary component was postulated by familial cases.

Modern understanding: It is now believed that anomalies in adipose tissue or a component of Dercum's illness. Obesity, metabolic problem and a higher frequency in middle-aged, postmenopausal women are frequently linked to it. Although the precise cause is yet unknown, a mix of genetic, metabolic, and potentially autoimmune variables are thought to be involved^{19,24,25,26,27}.

3. DRUGS USED IN DERCUM'S DISEASE

3.1 Corticosteroids:

These drugs work as anti-inflammatory agents by inhibiting the immune system and lowering inflammation (e.g. Prednisone).

MOA: By reducing the generation of inflammatory molecules and regulating the immunological response, corticosteroids diminish inflammation.

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

- Weight gain
- Hyperglycemia and Diabetes
- Osteoporosis
- Hypertension
- Muscle weakness

USE: They can aid in lowering discomfort and inflammation brought on by lipomas.

3.2 Nonsteroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs):

NSAIDs are useful treating inflammation and pain (e.g. Ibuprofen).

MOA: Prostaglandins, which are implicated in inflammation and pain signaling, are produced at a lower rate when NSAIDs inhibit the cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes.

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

- Gastrointestinal issues
- Cardiovascular risks
- Kidney damage

USE: They are used to relieve inflammation and pain.

3.3 Antidepressants:

Antidepressants drugs are used to treat the illness's related pain and emotional suffering (e.g. Duloxetine and Amitriptyline).

MOA: Amitriptyline is a tricyclic antidepressant that works by preventing serotonin and norepinephrine from being absorbed. Serotonin-Norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs) include duloxetine.

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

Duloxetine:

- **Gastrointestinal issues-** nausea, dry mouth
- **CNS-** dizziness, headache, insomnia
- **Cardiovascular-** hypertension
- **Hepatic-** liver damage

Amitriptyline:

- **Anticholinergic effects**- blurred vision, constipation
- **Cardiovascular**- tachycardia
- **CNS**- drowsiness, dizziness
- Weight gain

USE: These medications are used to treat pain since they have ability to modulate it, particularly in causes of chronic pain.

3.4 Anticonvulsants:

Anticonvulsant drugs, sometimes referred to as Antiepileptic drugs (AEDs), due to its capacity to calm nerve activity and decrease pain. AEDs are frequently used in the treatment of chronic pain syndromes, including Dercum's illness (e.g. gabapentin and pregabalin).

MOA: This mechanism involves binding to the central nervous system's voltage-gated calcium channels alpha-2-delta subunit, which in turn decreases the release of excitatory neurotransmitters.

ADVERSE EFFECTS:**Gabapentin:**

- Dizziness
- Fatigue
- Ataxia (lack of muscle coordination)
- Peripheral edema

Pregabalin:

- Muscle pain
- Allergic reactions
- Angioedema
- Blurred vision

USE: Neuropathic pain is treated with them.

3.5 Lidocaine (topical or systemic):

Lidocaine is local anesthetic, frequently used to treat the discomfort brought by this illness.

MOA: Lidocaine inhibits sodium channels to stop nerve impulses from starting and conduction.

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

- **Local pain**- redness, swelling at the site of injection
- **Systemic reaction**- nervousness, tremors, itching, rash
- Methemoglobinemia

USE: To treat localized pain, it can be used topically or systemically.

3.6 Methotrexate:

It is used in the management of Dercum's illness, a rare disorder marked by excruciating lipomas.

MOA: By blocking dihydrofolate reductase, methotrexate reduces the production of proteins, RNA, and DNA, which in turn can alter the immune system.

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

- **Hepatotoxicity**- liver damage
- **Gastrointestinal issues**- nausea, vomiting, diarrhea
- **Dermatologic effects**- rash, alopecia (hair loss)
- **Neurological effects**- headache, dizziness
- Hematologic effects
- Pulmonary toxicity
- Renal toxicity

USE: Because of its immunosuppressive and anti-inflammatory qualities, it is sometimes utilized in this situation^{28,29,30,31}.

4. Diagnosis of dercum's disease**✚ Based on symptoms:**

Based on the observation of symptoms and the rule out of any associated conditions, the condition's clinical diagnosis is made. In cases where certain symptoms are absent, the diagnosis is made using a narrow set of clinical criteria.

- Overweight or generalized obesity
- The existence of chronic pain in the adipose tissue that lasts longer than 3 months.

The diagnosis of several diseases linked to fat buildup is covered in article, including Madelung's illness, fibromyalgia, lipoedema, and dercum's disease. Certain molecules in the blood and cerebral fluid of 53 patients with dercum's illness were discovered to have changed, which may indicate that these compounds are involved in pain signaling. Rheumatologic testing should be carried out to rule out DD, as there are currently no laboratory tests created particularly for this diagnosis.

4.1 Imaging appearance:

Lesions in the superficial subcutaneous fat were identified using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasound; deep fat remained unharmed. Lesions were more easily found by imaging techniques than by physical examination, proving that they were asymptomatic. According to Tins et al. (2013), the majority of lesions were rectangular, smaller than 2 cm in diameter, and oriented parallel to the skin longitudinally. Hyperechoic lesions without any surrounding edema or visible flow on Doppler imaging were found on ultrasound. Reduced T1-

weighted signal and increased water-sensitive signal on MRI revealed a blush-like appearance. Lesions that were symptomatic and those that were asymptomatic did not differ much, while larger

lesions seemed more uneven. It is possible to spot lipomas stalked or lodged inside swelling subcutaneous fat tissue on computed tomography (CT) pictures.

Fig no.4.1(A) MRI

(B) Ultra sound

4.2 Histopathology:

A histological investigation of the lipoma can demonstrate the benignity or lipomatous nature of the adipose tissue, even though biomarkers linked to Dercum's disease are still unknown. Because connective tissue and fibrosis predominate in Dercum's disease, adipose tissue may be less metabolically active. The presence of multinucleated giant cells in the adipose tissue of patients with Dercum's disease indicates that pro-inflammatory activated macrophages are involved in both the development of adipose tissue and resistance to weight loss. A milder inflammatory response in Dercum's disease adipose tissue compared to lean obese controls is another indication that obesity, not the disease itself, is associated to inflammation.

Fig no.4.2 Histopathology

✚ Related disorder:

❖ Fibromyalgia:

Widespread muscle soreness and painful reaction to pressure on at least 11 out of 18 distinct tender point locations are symptoms of fibromyalgia. Numerous other symptoms, including weariness, sleep difficulties and depressive symptoms, are linked into it. The cause is unclear and the distinction from Dercum's illness can occasionally be arbitrary-particularly when the patient is obese.

❖ Lipoedema:

A chronic condition mainly affecting women, lipoedema is characterized by symmetrical swelling of the lower limbs brought on by a build-up of subcutaneous adipose tissue. Usually starting in adolescence, the issue gradually gets worse and causes tenderness when palpated. Due to concomitant ambulation problems, individuals with morbid obesity and chronic lipoedema may also develop lipolymphoedema, a secondary mechanical insufficiency of the lymphatic system that can result in edematous fluid accumulation and ultimately pulmonary edema.

❖ **Panniculitis:**

An inflammatory condition affecting subcutaneous adipose tissue, typified by skin nodules that are painful to the touch and systemic symptoms. The diagnosis after a skin biopsy determines the kind and amount of subcutaneous inflammatory infiltrates (neutrophils, histiocytes, lymphocytes, granulomas), as well as any septal or lobular characteristics.

Endocrine disorders:

Obesity and psychiatric symptoms can coexist with widespread pain in some endocrine conditions. Cushing's syndrome, for instance (corticotropin-independent adrenal hyperfunction), is typified by aching joints and a progressive emergence of obesity, usually centered on the trunk, back, and face (also known as "buffalo hump" and "moon face"). Furthermore, most patients experience psychological symptoms such as sadness, emotional instability, and irritability. Hypothyroidism is another endocrine disease that can weight gain and pain in the limbs. Oedema of the hands, feet and face are additional symptoms of myxoedema. Patients with endocrine abnormalities typically do not experience pain from adipose tissue.

❖ **Lipodystrophies:**

A characteristic of lipodystrophies is the selective loss of body fat from various body regions. Adipose tissue loss can be localized, leaving distinct subcutaneous zones, or substantial, leaving body fat absent throughout. Lipodystrophies can be of two types: Acquired (like Lawrence syndrome and Barraquer-Simons syndrome) Congenital (like Berardinelli-Seip syndrome). Nonetheless, the majority of people undergoing liposuction for cosmetic purposes have localized excess fat accumulation, which is also known as lipodystrophy. Moreover, lipodystrophies include patients without pain and with a distribution of fat similar to lipoedema.

❖ **Proteus syndrome:**

The rare disease known as Proteus syndrome is characterized by the rapid and uneven growth of several tissue types, including skin, bones, blood vessels, fat, and connective tissue. This disorder is brought on by a mosaic activating mutation in the AKT1 oncogene.

❖ **Multiple symmetric lipomatosis:**

Large subcutaneous fatty lumps distributed symmetrically throughout the neck, shoulders, upper extremities, trunk, and occasionally intrathoracic region are the main characteristic of multiple symmetric lipomatosis. According to epidemiology, the disease is more common in

men and is frequently linked to alcoholism. Most of the time, the fat deposits are not as painful. Familial multiple lipomatosis is the term used when multiple lipomatosis is inherited in an autosomal-dominant manner. An A to G mutation at mitochondrial DNA location A8344 may be linked to the illness. Since multiple symmetric lipomatosis's fatty lumps are not painful, it can be distinguished from Dercum's illness. Different from familial multiple lipomatosis is multiple symmetric lipomatosis.

❖ **Neurofibromatosis type I:**

Subcutaneous neurofibromas, which produce discomfort and neurological symptoms, can occur in certain patients with neurofibromatosis type I (Von Recklinghausen's disease). From a pathohistological perspective, neurofibromas differ from lipomas.

❖ **Adipose tissue tumors:**

Malignant adipose tissue tumors, either single or numerous, are well-differentiated adipocyte-based subcutaneous tumors. Different types of lipomas exist, some of which are often painful. Although extremely rare, malignant cutaneous adipose tissue neoplasms are typically not unpleasant. These tumors include liposarcomas, cutaneous spindle cell/pleomorphic lipomas, cutaneous angiolipoleiomyoma (also known as "Angiomyolipoma"), and adenolipoma of the skin. Since tumors don't hurt, they can typically be distinguished from Dercum's disease with ease.

❖ **Multiple endocrine neoplasia I (MEN I):**

Although they are not painful, numerous lipomas and other subcutaneous tumors can occasionally be seen in patients with multiple endocrine neoplasia I (MEN I). Since the lipomas in MEN I are not painful, it is simple to distinguish MEN I from Dercum's disease.

❖ **Myoclonic epilepsy with ragged red fibres (merrf):**

Multiple symmetric lipomatosis can occasionally coexist with MERRF, a hereditary mitochondrial disorder. A mutation in the mitochondrial DNA tRNA gene at location 8344 is the most frequent cause. Because the lipomas in MERRF are not painful, it is simple to distinguish MERRF from Dercum's illness^{6,9}.

5. TREATMENT**5.1 Pain management:**✚ **Medications:**

❖ **Anti-depressants:** For neuropathic pain, serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors

(e.g. duloxetine) and tricyclic antidepressants (e.g. amitriptyline).

- ❖ **Nonsteroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs):** NSAIDs medications (e.g. Ibuprofen) are used to treat mild to severe pain.
- ❖ **Anticonvulsants:** Neuropathic pain may be treated with gabapentin or pregabalin.
- ❖ **Lidocaine:** For localized pain relief, use capsaicin creams or lidocaine patches^{32,33}.

5.2 Non-Pharmacological Treatments

Lifestyle Modifications:

✚ Diet:

Anti-inflammatory foods such as fruits, vegetables, and omega-3 fatty acids can be included in a diet to assist lessen pain and inflammation.

✚ Exercise:

Walking or swimming are two low-impact activities that might assist increase circulation and decrease inflammation.

✚ Sleep:

Making sure you get enough sleep and practicing excellent sleep hygiene will help you manage the discomfort and exhaustion that come with having Dercum disease.

✚ Weight management:

Reducing pressure on the afflicted areas and easing discomfort can be achieved by maintaining a healthy weight.

✚ Stress management:

Since stress exacerbates symptoms, it is helpful to practice relaxation techniques like yoga, meditation, and deep breathing³⁴.

5.3 Physical therapy:

- **Manual lymphatic Drainage:** By encouraging the flow of lymphatic fluid, this method helps lessen discomfort and edema.
- **Stretching and strengthening exercises:** Personalized exercise regimen can increase muscle flexibility and strength, which can aid with pain management and improve physical function.
- **Pain reduction methods:** To lessen pain, physical therapists may use techniques including electrical stimulation, heat, and cold therapy.
- **Massage therapy:** Because the affected areas are sensitive, care must be used when providing a gentle massage to ease discomfort and promote circulation.

5.4 Psychological support:

- **Counselling and therapy:** Patients who are experiencing pain or mental distress can benefit from psychotherapy, particularly cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT).

Changing negative thought patterns and improving coping techniques are two areas where CBT is most helpful.

- **Mindfulness and relaxation techniques:** Pain treatment and stress reduction are aided by methods like yoga, mindfulness meditation, and deep breathing exercises.
- **Support groups:** Attending support groups facilitates the sharing of experiences and coping mechanisms while also offering emotional support and lowering feelings of loneliness.
- **Educational resources:** Giving patients and their family thorough knowledge about Dercum's illness might empower them and lessen their fear about the unknown components of the condition.
- **Family and caregiver support:** By creating a supportive atmosphere, educating, and including family members in the care process improves the patient's psychological wellbeing.

5.5 Surgical and interventional procedures:

- ✚ **Liposuction:** There have been several cases of liposuction patients reported. Suction-assisted liposuction was utilized in each instance. Except for one researcher who employed the tumescence technique with a 0.1 percent pilocarpine solution, all investigators employed the "dry" technique. The destruction of nerve plexuses in the adipose tissue is assumed to be the mechanism causing pain alleviation after liposuction. But it is unclear that the decrease observed after liposuction can be explained by direct loss of nerves alone. Additionally, after liposuction in healthy patients, the pain decreases in Dercum's condition lasted longer than the typical sensitivity loss. A few cases have been attempted with lipectomy. Although the treatment was successful, all but one of the subjects had discomfort again.

- ✚ **Surgical excision:** When analgesics and psychotherapy failed to yield sufficient comfort, surgical excision is a viable option for certain problematic lesions. Although it can provide symptomatic relief, the operation carries the standard risks of surgery and may not stop lipomas from recurring^{35,36,37}.

5.6 Alternative therapies:

✚ Acupuncture:

Inserting tiny needles into predetermined body locations to encourage healing and alleviate pain is one way that acupuncture helps some people find pain relief

✚ Herbal Remedies:

A few herbal medicines, like ginger and turmeric, which are well-known for their anti-inflammatory qualities, may help lessen pain and inflammation. These, however, ought to be used under a doctor's supervision^{38,39,40}.

5.7 Investigational therapies:

5.7.1 Calcium-channel modulators:

Numerous calcium-channel modulators have been tested, including the anticonvulsants pregabalin (Lyrica®) and oxcarbazepine (Trileptal®). It prevents chemicals like excitatory amino acids-which are essentials for central sensitization-from being released by blocking the activation of neuronal calcium channels. Neuropathic pain is treated with these medications. Many of these compounds have a wide spectrum of pharmacological effects, and their efficacy in treating neuropathic pain may be attributed to mechanisms other than calcium-channel regulation.

5.7.2 Rapid cycling hypobaric pressure:

Patients with Dercum's illness may experience less discomfort if fast cyclic hypobaric pressure is administered, according to pilot research with ten patients. Various processes have been suggested to explain the impact, including intermittent compression improving blood flow, pneumatic displacement of fluid, which reduces tissue oedema, a rise in arterial oxygen saturation, and a decrease in hypoxia in the painful region.

5.7.3 Frequency Rhythmic Electrical Modulation System (FREMS):

FREMS is an electrotherapy that uses a software-driven method to control electrical stimulation. The large range of frequencies utilized, primarily between 1 and 50 Hz, can lessen interference from illnesses and support healthy brain circuits. Increased blood flow with FREMS therapy may lessen lipedema discomfort brought on by inflammation, adipocyte necrosis, and hypoxia. In painful adipose tissue, vascular endothelial growth factor released following therapy may further improve blood flow and lessen hypoxia.

5.7.4 MC5-A Calmare therapy:

Early experiments show that a novel neuromodulation tool for electro cutaneous nerve stimulation is successful in treating difficult-to-treat chronic pain. The device should not be used by those who have automated defibrillators, vena cava clips,

skull plates, pacemakers, aneurysm clips, untreated pain, epilepsy, or who are pregnant. These people should not have electrodes put on their skulls or on their carotid sinuses, and before using any electrodes, a cost-benefit analysis should be done.

5.7.5 Prognosis:

The natural course of Dercum's disease has not been thoroughly studied, although case studies have indicated that the discomfort may worsen with time. A recent study with a five-year follow-up, however, does not provide compelling evidence for this. Over the course of the 5 years in that study, the average pain level remained largely stable at roughly a 5 out of 10. After 5 years, some patients reported reduced pain on an individual basis, while others reported more⁶.

CONCLUSION:

Chronic and disabling, Dercum's illness is typified by excruciating lipomas and a host of related symptoms such as weariness, emotional dysphoria, and cognitive decline. Although it has a major influence on patients' quality of life, the cause and pathophysiology are still mostly unknown, and there is no known treatment. The current focus of treatment is on managing symptoms with drugs, surgery, physical therapy, and mental health assistance. To understand the fundamental causes of Dercum's disease and create more specialized and efficient treatments, more investigation is required. Better diagnosis and treatment of this uncommon illness may result from increased knowledge and comprehension among medical professionals.

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